

Marketing Strategy of OPPO Mobile Phone in Pakistan

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Abstract:

As an emerging smart phone consumer market in recent years, Pakistan has a low domestic smart phone penetration rate and a huge number of potential smart phone users. This study takes the marketing of OPPO mobile phone in Pakistan as the research object, uses 7P theory to analyze the marketing case of OPPO mobile phone in Pakistan, and puts forward some optimization suggestions in terms of product, price, channel, promotion, personnel, tangible display and process. The research methodology employed in this study is centered around the administration of a questionnaire survey, which aims to provide a comprehensive analysis of the

research conducted on onions. Through the optimization of OPPO mobile phone strategy in Pakistan, this study hopes to actively explore the international market and optimize the localization strategy for Chinese mobile phone brands represented by OPPO mobile phone.

Keywords: *OPPO mobile company, mobile marketing, smartphone, SWOT analysis.*

Introduction

Intelligent manufacturing has allowed for the rise of a new manufacturing mode: customized production (Niaz et al., 2021; and Shoukat et al., 2022). At times, machines are utilized to perform

mundane, uninteresting chores that humans used to do in order to suit people's individual demands and make manufacturing more efficient (Nawaz et al., 2022; and Shoukat et al., 2023 and 2022). The mobile sector in China has had moderate growth over the past decade,

primarily attributed to breakthroughs in science and technology, particularly in communications innovation. Chinese multi-purpose brands, namely Huawei, OPPO, VIVO, and Xiaomi, have experienced significant growth, leading to a steady reduction in the gap between these brands and industry leaders such as Apple and Samsung.

According to Porter's five forces model, customers have little leverage to negotiate better prices or terms when purchasing goods or services (Anastasiu et al., 2020). Due mostly to a lack of foreign rivalry and multinational firms, there is a low possibility of new entrants and a small number of companies in the market. Many companies have made international growth a priority since the late 1970s, when major players in the market made the decision to enter the global market (Andersson et al., 2004). According to the principles of microeconomics, the supplier has monopoly power over the market when demand is high. Customers are more likely to rapidly remember the goods when there is less competition in the market and strong expectations among buyers (Monroe et al., 1999). As time progresses, we enter a period of unprecedented levels of competitiveness as a result of unprecedented levels of competition and globalization.

It has been noted that the e-commerce industry has had a profound effect on the corporate environment, resulting in revolutionary shifts in company processes. Seventy percent of stores, according to a survey, are expected to be online-only by the year 2500, meaning brick-and-mortar stores would close down. Competition in the corporate world is tough, thus advertising and marketing are more important than ever (Bryla et al., 2018). Advertising is the process of drawing attention to a business through the use of various media, including print media, television, and billboards (Hidayet et al., 2018). Most advertising agencies advise repeat airings of commercials for the same product so that viewers will retain more of the information presented.

According to Ye et al. (2014), the marketing and advertising divisions of a firm take up a sizable chunk of the company's revenue and earnings.

The departments listed above are commonly acknowledged as the company's main creative force, charged with coming up with groundbreaking strategies to increase product sales and boost overall revenue. Product promotion is a proven, effective strategy for raising brand awareness and driving sales. When introducing a new product or growing an existing line, businesses often run promotional campaigns. Attracting potential customers with the hope of convincing them to make a purchase is the primary goal of product advertising (Aghara et al., 2018). However, businesses readily adopt the practice of product promotions as a strategy to tempt clients, considering the importance of innovation in encouraging growth. The primary goal of this research is to look into the factors that contribute to smartphone reliance in the workplace, and to see if such a small device can be beneficial or harmful to the people who use it every day. In addition, the global rising trends in smartphone usage justify a thorough investigation of those elements (Shin et al. 2009). The study's overarching objective is to learn whether or not employees' smartphone dependence has a positive or negative effect on their productivity on the job. In addition, the information presented here is instructive for other mobile device producers. In light of the research, the following objectives have been proposed.

- To Evaluate the impact of advertising and promotional activities on the sales performance of OPPO phones in the Pakistani market.
- The objective of this study is to evaluate the influence of advertising on the sales performance of OPPO mobile phones in the Pakistani market.
- To evaluate the impact of marketing strategies on the sales performance of OPPO mobile phones in Pakistan.

The rest of research after introduction was based on a background and methods, which demonstrated fundamental points such as PEST analysis method, five force model and SWOT analysis method. Section 3 analyzed the case

study and results. Section 4 shown the detailed summary on discussion and section 5 presented the conclusion of this study.

Background and Methods

PEST Analysis Method

PEST analysis is a strategic management tool that stands for political, economic, social, and technological factors. It is used to assess the macro-environmental factors that can affect an organization or a specific project. Here's a brief description of how this might apply to OPPO in Pakistan,

The political factors include government policies, stability, trade tariffs, tax policies, and regulations that can affect the business environment. For OPPO in Pakistan, this might involve understanding things like import/export regulations, government policies on technology, and any political instability that could impact operations.

The economic factors involve assessing the economic conditions of the country. This includes factors like inflation rates, exchange rates, interest rates, and overall economic growth. For OPPO, it's important to consider the purchasing power of consumers in Pakistan, as well as economic trends that might affect the demand for mobile phones.

Social factors relate to cultural, demographic, and societal trends. For OPPO in Pakistan, it could involve understanding the preferences of consumers, their lifestyles, cultural norms, and any specific social trends that might affect the demand for mobile phones.

Technological factors involve evaluating the level of technology adoption, research and development activity, and the rate of innovation in the market. For OPPO, this could include considerations about the technological infrastructure in Pakistan, the level of smartphone penetration, and any emerging technologies that could impact the industry.

Five Force Model

The Five Forces Model, which Michael Porter established, serves as a conceptual framework for examining the competitive dynamics of a given industry. This factor facilitates the assessment of market attractiveness and profitability. When applied to OPPO, a mobile company in Pakistan, the analysis might look like this,

Threat of New Entrants: In Pakistan's mobile market, there is a moderate threat of new entrants. While the market is lucrative due to a large consumer base, it is also highly competitive with established players like Samsung, Apple, and local brands. OPPO has built a brand presence, but new entrants can still challenge its market share.

Bargaining Power of Suppliers: Suppliers in the mobile industry usually have a moderate to high bargaining power. This is because they provide critical components (like processors, screens, etc.) that are essential for manufacturing. OPPO, being a well-established brand, might have some leverage in negotiations, but the power still lies with the suppliers.

Bargaining Power of Buyers: In Pakistan's mobile market, buyers have a considerable amount of bargaining power. There is a wide range of options available, from high-end to budget smartphones, giving consumers ample choice. If OPPO's products are not competitively priced or do not meet consumer expectations, they can easily switch to other brands.

Threat of Substitutes: The threat of substitutes in the mobile industry is relatively high. Consumers can choose from a variety of alternatives such as laptops, tablets, or even use multiple devices for different tasks. This means OPPO needs to continuously innovate and provide unique features to differentiate itself.

Competitive Rivalry: The competitive rivalry in Pakistan's mobile market is intense. OPPO competes with both international giants like Samsung and Apple, as well as local players like Huawei, Vivo, and Infinix. These companies are constantly striving to gain market share, which drives innovation, price competition, and aggressive marketing campaigns.

SWOT Analysis Method

Strong brand presence: OPPO has established itself as a reputable and recognizable brand in the Pakistani mobile market. **Innovative Technology:** Known for introducing innovative features and technologies in their smartphones. **Diverse Product Range:** Offers a wide range of smartphones catering to different market segments and consumer preferences. **Effective Marketing Strategies:** Utilizes effective marketing campaigns to reach a broad audience in Pakistan. **Robust Distribution Network:** OPPO has an extensive distribution network across Pakistan, ensuring availability in both urban and rural areas.

Intense competition: Faces stiff competition from other established smartphone brands in Pakistan like Samsung, Huawei, Xiaomi, and others. **Price Sensitivity:** The Pakistani market is price-sensitive, and OPPO's premium pricing may be a barrier for some consumers. **Limited Market Share:** While popular, OPPO might have a smaller market share compared to some of its competitors. **Perceived Lack of Differentiation:** Some consumers might perceive OPPO's products as like other Android smartphones in the market.

Rising smartphone adoption: Pakistan has a growing smartphone market, presenting opportunities for increased sales and market share. **Focus on Mid-Range Segment:** There is a significant demand for mid-range smartphones in Pakistan, which could be an area for OPPO to focus on. **Investment in 5G Technology:** With the global shift towards 5G, investing in this technology in Pakistan could give OPPO an edge. **Expanding Ecosystem:** Introducing complementary products and services (smart accessories, wearables, etc.) could enhance OPPO's presence in the market.

Economic instability: Economic fluctuations and uncertainty in Pakistan's economy can affect consumer spending on non-essential items like smartphones. **Regulatory Changes:** Changes in import/export policies or other regulatory hurdles can impact OPPO's operations in Pakistan. **Emerging Competitors:** New entrants or the growth of existing competitors can

challenge OPPO's market position. **Technological Shifts:** Rapid changes in technology trends may require constant innovation and adaptation to stay competitive.

Case Study and Results

Product

The dissemination and collection of this questionnaire occurred through many channels, including email, WeChat, live distribution, and Google form. Moreover, after getting the result of the analyzed data based on the questionnaire consist of eight questions that has been asked. Figure 1 is identified in yes and No answers of people. The answer to every question is different. People think differently about the products of OPPO mobile phone. Most people want to use high-quality products. Some people are satisfied with the OPPO mobile phone supply companies offering high-quality goods, and some stay neutral. OPPO mobile phone in high-competition areas face a challenge in maintaining their competitive advantage by providing exceptional service.

The higher score in this dimension, the higher customer satisfaction with the product. The results of this product survey were analyzed using the Likert scale. The average score of this dimension was 3.20, which did not reach the level of satisfaction (4 points). According to the data, customers that there are more products has complete range and that is more convenient than the average, but the company products has is as high as 166%. The analysis of the results is shown in the figure below.

OPPO Mobile Phone Company will need to be mindful of the client's requirements Client relationships, like personal relationships, are a two-way street; companies must connect with their clients to get them to communicate. Retail OPPO mobile phone customers will not feel a genuine bond with the Company unless it treats in interactive courting. Marketing network comes to the independent OPPO mobile phone they cannot find anywhere else. Developing customer service strengths can be achieved by acknowledging and analyzing customer service

failures experienced by customers at prominent chain stores or other independent OPPO mobile phone retailers.

Cause of Price issues

The cost of a product is a fundamental determinant. The determination of the price necessitates a thorough examination of the market (Figure 2). Typically, organizations engage in market research prior to establishing pricing strategies.

Figure 1. Response on Product Information

The higher the score of this dimension, the higher the customer satisfaction in terms of price. The results of this survey of products were analyzed by the Likert scale. The average score of this dimension was 3.19, and the degree of recognition in terms of price did not reach the level of agreement (4 points). According to the data, the degree of approval of customers for the strong discounts and rich activities is the same as the average value, but only 166% of the people who “agree” account for less than half of them. The recognition degree of attractiveness is even lower than the average value. Therefore, company A has a problem in product pricing. The analysis is shown in the figure below.

Moreover, the most crucial price must be set according to the quality of products. The result of the survey about price is given in figure 3.2.

Fifty-eight participants answered these questions. The majority of people want to purchase high-quality OPPO mobile and are apathetic about the cost. However, most people think that OPPO mobile phone did not train the bazaar to magistrate the market strains. Mostly due to that the price will increase, people are not satisfied with the price and quality. People think the price must be according to the products' quality. People did not buy products at high prices based on rigorous needs. Clarify the scope of goods, hours, and place to the authorized website, and feature academic literature simply available at the store. Most significantly, ensure company and company employees always answer questions, and publicity and public relation to enhancing photographs of OPPO mobile phone or other features.

Figure 2. Response on Price Information

Cause of Place issues

In contemporary society, individuals are preoccupied with their daily routines and commitments. The majority of individuals are unable to allocate time for physically visiting the market and purchasing things after making a selection. Consequently, enterprises generally offer the convenience of delivering their products directly to the customer's location, as shown in Figure 3.

There is a positive correlation between the score of this dimension and consumer satisfaction

with regards to Place. The results of this survey of products were analyzed by the Likert scale. The average score of this dimension was 3.25, and the degree of recognition in terms of Place did not reach the level of agreement (4 points). According to the data, the degree of approval of customers for the trading channels is the same as the average value, but only 177% of the people who “agree” account for less than half of them. The recognition degree of attractiveness is even lower than the average value. Therefore, company A has a problem in company sales support. The analysis is shown in the figure below:

Figure 3. Response on Place Information

In Figure 3, the findings pertaining to OPPO mobile phones Company subsequent to the survey are presented in Figure 3.4. The reduction of "friction" within the sales process directly correlates with the facilitation of a favorable client experience when utilizing an OPPO mobile phone. Any steps that business leaders can take to make their products and services more available are enormously beneficial. The company must think about these problems and solve customer problems to win the customer's hearts. OPPO mobile phone should use that knowledge to improve the customer experience. Customer support is insufficient on its own. It must be backed up by the high-quality goods have.

People

In OPPO mobile phones' marketing strategy in Pakistan, the role of "people" is pivotal, as shown in Figure 4. This encompasses the company's internal teams, including sales, customer service, research, development,

marketing, and CSR professionals, who collectively shape the brand's image and customer experience. Additionally, external figures like brand ambassadors and influencers play a significant role in connecting with the target audience.

The higher the score of this dimension, the higher the customer satisfaction in terms of People. The results of this survey of products were analyze by the Likert scale. The average score of this dimension was 3.22, and the degree recognition in terms of People did not reach the level of agreement (4 points). According to the data, the degree of approval of customers for the marketing activities is the same as the average value, but only 166% of the people who "agree" account for less than half of them. The recognition degree of attractiveness is even lower than the average value. Therefor company A has problem in training. The analysis is shown in the figure below:

Figure 4. Response on People Information

It can be seen form Figure 4 that the competence, professionalism, and customer-centric approach of these individuals directly impact consumer perception and purchasing

decisions. The People contemplate that find OPPO mobile phone goods are easy to search out. Moreover, they think that they can find many branches in their neighboring area. Here is

the most important thing that has been asked in the thesis was: Does the OPPO mobile phone in Pakistan and China have appropriate & strategic locations? Most people say no. It means there is a big gap between these two countries related to OPPO mobile phone products. Most people used telephone or email and gave their order to the customer. However, they think contacting the medical companies is not easy, so they often ignore their email or did not receive any call. It means customers are not satisfied with the service of the company. Overall, OPPO's success in Pakistan hinges on effective communication, product innovation, and a strong network of engaged individuals who drive brand loyalty and market growth.

Discussion

Improvement of Price Strategy

The competition in OPPO is fierce, but it is a monopolistic competition because due to many factors, each enterprise charges different prices based on its performance, product feasibility, and target market. OPPO's smartphone prices are relatively high. When we talk about tablets, their quality and design are both excellent, suitable for the elite class, who have gained many technological benefits that are not within the commercial scope. The pricing policy followed by OPPO cannot be easily evaluated as the company did not specify the system. However, most companies, including this one, use cost-based pricing models (Zha et al., 2023). However, a company cannot adopt a single approach simultaneously, as its impact on the telecommunications product market based on price smoothness and consumer value will be unstable. A pricing policy has been established between OPPO and Samsung. They also agreed to maintain the price of the product; They also decided to develop a cost + reward strategy. Manpower, machinery, and electricity.

System Guarantee

The OPPO company facility in Kern County, California, USA is located at a distance of 640 acres, square mile, sq. ft process and storage. There is 375,000 sq. ft in the house. The facility

provides its own water treatment facilities and is capable of functioning independently of urban and regional infrastructure. Co-generation produces electricity of 6.2 MW. In the process for heating water and oil the cogeneration plant also produces steam. The plant receives 1,2 million gallons of water per day from two household wells, which also serve as fire safety emergency storage. The facility provides a 325-acre alfalfa field wastewater processing facility. With recent plant extensions, the manufacturing processes will be developed on 10 different product lines with more than 525SKU. The plant has an annual production capacity of over 127,000,000 lbs or 2442,307 lbs per week which is equal to 2,000,000 lbs per day. Every day 97,692 cases are handled in 16 truck docks and received from the logistical and storage viewpoint. Kern has more than 750 staff and is one of the leading facilities in Pakistan today. At this point the Frito-Lay Kern plant has invested heavily in its production.

Cultural Guarantee

The primary participants in this study consist of females, homemakers, and individuals in their youth. To what extent has consumption been prevalent among individuals? Nevertheless, their choice of target family is driven by their comprehensive understanding of the influential aspects inside this particular domain. From an economic standpoint, the business model of OPPO smartphones is advantageous for various income classes, excluding the working class. The legally authorized firm "OPPO" in Pakistan has broadened the extent of government participation through the implementation of labor and business regulations. However, it is widely recognized that such restrictions have significant implications for government engagement within any given institution. Moreover, if these limitations are imposed, they have the potential to impede progress and hinder organizational development.

Hence, the implementation of stringent governmental laws may result in a discrepancy between the future objectives and accomplishments of Oppo mobile. Natural lakes can be likened to organic byproducts of plant

extrusion, since they do not impose any adverse impacts on the environment and serve as valuable natural assets. In the present scenario, the potential for a scarcity of essential resources is exceptionally high. The OPPO brand, in and of itself, is not subject to the influence of changes in tradition and culture, both at the primary and secondary levels. The communities residing in South Asia, specifically the subcontinent, as well as Pakistan, have experienced an outbreak of infection. Smartphones have gained global recognition as prominent goods in the international technology business. The utilization of contemporary technologies has resulted in enhanced efficiency and increased quality.

Conclusion

The primary objective of this study is to examine multiple factors that influence brand loyalty, with a specific emphasis on exploring strategies related to the graphic marketing mix. The OPPO smartphone company demonstrates a strong commitment to delivering exceptional customer service. By aligning their product offerings with the specific demands and preferences of their clients, the company has experienced a notable growth in its customer base. Several aspects might influence brand loyalty, such as the absence of recommendations, promotional offerings, customer complaints, the speed of delivery for OPPO mobile phones, delivery reliability, and monthly payments associated with OPPO phone usage. These elements have both positive and negative effects. The research methodology employed in this study relies on sampling techniques, as the target population is extensive and actual data must be gathered to assess the efficacy of the study. The study employed the deductive technique to examine the elements that influence brand loyalty within the context of Pakistan's OPPO firm.

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Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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